

Exploring the dominant factors while adoption of new innovative fashion cloths in rural areas of district Khairpur

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ABSTRACT

The survey data was collected to find out the factors considered by rural population while adopting innovative fashion clothes. Survey was conducted through questionnaires.

SPSS 16.0 Software is used for analyzing the quantitative data. These factors would be helpful for the marketers and manufacturers of cloth producers to design the products according to the demands of population of rural area. According to the frequency distribution analysis and nominal regression result shows that people of rural areas influenced by focus groups, and fashion clothes enhance their personality and fashion clothes fulfills their demands. Same time it affects culture, society and religious values. As fashion clothes are costly for them so they cannot afford these clothes. They feel that old fashion is better than new fashion. Factors like focus group enhanced personality influence the customers of rural areas to adopt the fashion clothes while cost of obtaining fashion clothes and some societal factors discourage them to adopt new fashion clothes.

Key words: - frequency distribution, innovative, culture, RMG.

INTRODUCTION

Objective of this research is to provide the understanding of factors to be considered by the manufacturer of fashion clothes while designing innovative fashion clothes for rural areas. We developed hypothesis that residence of urban are highly innovative in adopting the fashion clothes or rural consumers are low innovative than urban consumers.

Innovation is continuous process, and need practical approach to implement the idea. It is job of inventor to put that creative idea into practice. Successful inventors have the ability to commercialize new concept and provide solution to an old problem. Innovation is not a process where culture is big challenge. Successful innovators know the basic hurdles and know very well how to deal with them and have ability to select the idea plan it and execute that plan, because culture obstacle and risk of failure is associated with the plan.

Now a day's every ones dream is innovative change in fashion of clothes, companies are trying to produce the products through which they want to satisfy the needs and wants of customers, but it is very difficult to know/understand psychology of customers accompanies are trying to get feedback from customers in many ways. For producing new product it is necessary to know about the different variable just like Religion, Culture, psychology and income of customers.

Our research will helpful for those companies who want to know about the customer's needs and wants either they are innovative in nature or not they want change or

not we have focused the rural areas of district Khairpur, and result will be applicable for this specific area if any company wants to launch new product for this region.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(jadhav & patil, february 2012) he said that over the period of few years, the women's which are working, fashion trends are changing, increasing in information and media, and marketing of foreign brands have given a industry a total new dimension. As a result the organizations who are working to produce men's fashion products diversify to produce women's fashion clothes in order to exploit the market. Earlier most popular player's present only men's wear product in national level, but now a day's industries are focusing on women's more.

They find that women's are more flexible in changing situation of market, they are not static ideology-driven life style in their choice they usually need new thing. In future society needs to more versatile women. Women in the rural areas tended to be more conservative in their dressing than women living in urban areas. While coming to the city rural women dress up in well manner.

(sandraj, 6 august 2011) He said that at this time People's lives more difficult due to increasing cost of food, energy, and real estate, and we are making mistake to adopting the foreign fashion and now we have to decide that we are purchasing for our needs.

He further concluded that growing economy made more prosperous to the people and from his study one best situation comes out that young people's prefer domestic product more than western products, because the needs and wants of consumers are better understand by the domestic products, consumers deserve foreign products are not matches to our society and they have less knowledge about products.

(Islam, Islam, Anwarul Azim, Anwar, & Uddin, March 2014). They said that for any company it is necessary to know about the customer's needs and wants and society and they are talking about the Bangladesh customers that they are giving more preferences to the culture/traditional dresses for example men is Lungi, Panjabi, Gengi, and Shirt and for women is Shari. They said that early in the 1990 peoples was prefer local dress but due to the changes in globalization men's wear increased in wearing the foreign dresses and peoples are more attracted by the readymade dresses. In the mid of 2000 peoples mind was change from local products to international products.

Further they concluded that "it can be concluded that it is important to know the customers buying behavior process and customers requirements properly. The brand developer should develop and place the products accordingly to the customer and that will help in sustainable apparel products development as well as better business performances".

(BRANDES, 2009) He said that first half of the 20th American fashion omitted fashion from histories because the customer's need was the fabric use rather than the new garments style.

It is quite difficult to make something fashionable from some useful material it requires deep thinking and time to design the dress.

(Hubacek, Guan, & Barua, 2007) They concluded that with improved quality of life results the financial wellbeing in India and China. The population has practiced a transition from poverty to enough food and clothing. Rich life style is adopted in rising parts of population. They further concluded that peoples mind is changed they are adopting the readymade garments in sense that these are up to date and cope the needs of new fashion trends.

(Rayhan, saha, & Hassan, 5.03.2014) They are of the opinion that there are two broad categories of readymade garments first is woven second is knit garments. When there is heterogeneity in buying behavior of consumers makes challenging environment for marketers. Clothes are an epitome of a culture. People in different parts of the globe have their own styles of dressing which symbolize their culture and status. The past two

centuries have seen an upsurge in the use of manmade textiles like polyester, nylon, acrylic etc in almost every part of the world." They further concluded that largest contribution for economy is provided by the Ready Made Garments, hence it has the major role in the economy because the majority of foreign income comes from the this sector of RMG. They said that major challenge for sectors is that the change consumers buying behavior from cross the border or region to region.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quantitative data is used in this research, which is collected through primary source for which questionnaire was developed to get the responses from population of rural area of Khairpur. Simple random sampling technique is used for collecting the primary data. Factors which these customers could consider were included. The questionnaires were based on five ranking responses. Questionnaire contains 15 questions and we conducted survey from 100 respondents. SPSS 16.0 software is used to compile and interpret the results of the questionnaires. For this multi nominal regression and frequency distribution techniques are applied.

CONCLUSION

According to the frequency distribution analysis and multi nominal regression result shows that people of rural areas influenced by focus groups, and fashion clothes enhance their personality and fashion clothes fulfills their demands. Same time it affects culture, society and religious values. As fashion clothes are costly for them so they cannot afford these clothes. They feel that old fashion is better than new fashion. Hence the hypothesis was accepted that rural consumers are low innovative than urban consumers.

- The response which is taken from the respondents that 60 to 70 percent of respondent feels difficulty while purchasing the new fashion clothes because there is lack of advertisement and awareness in the mind of peoples they do not know that how to make the choice for the clothes and what are current fashion clothes available in the market so there is need of advertisement.
- More than 45% of respondents do not know about the choice of focus group just like actors cricketers or famous personalities because they are not interested in the focus group they do not want to depend on others they want their own choice because there is lack of knowledge and awareness.

- Most of respondent's response that new fashion can fulfill their demands but reason is that the new fashion is costly for them and most of respondents have low level of income that's why they do not want to adopt that new fashion of clothes.
- According to the opinion of respondents more than 60% responses that the new fashion of clothes affect their culture, society and religion because they do not think beyond these factors.
- One question asked by the respondent they responses that the new fashion can enhance their personality but they do not go through that because that new fashion is not reliable for the society culture and religion that is why they do not want to adopt new fashion of clothes.
- According to the responses most of respondents responses that they want to go through the old

fashion of clothes rather than the new fashion of clothes, because as it is mentioned in above statement that new fashion is not reliable for the culture society and religion, so peoples are not agree that new fashion is adopted by them.

SUGGESTIONS;

Factors which rural customers consider when they adopt new fashion clothes are limited only 15 factors considered for further research another factors should be included to find out more refined research.

LIMITATIONS;

This research was conducted at geographical location of rural areas of Khairpur District. Which has limited geographical coverage as regarding to the response is considered, it does not represent the trend of whole rural area of Pakistan. To get more specific result sample size may be increased to get the overall trend of rural areas.

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APPENDIX

Data Analysis:

Statistics

	you feel choice difficulty while purchasing the new fashion clothes	Actors/focus group can affect on your fashion of clothes	New fashion of clothes is affordable for you	Can new fashion of clothes fulfill your demand	You purchase on your choice or depend on others	Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your culture	Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your religion	Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is costly for you	Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is adopted by you	Do you feel that new fashion can make your personality better	In your opinion new fashion trends are better than old fashion trends	Do you think new fashion trends are enhancing your personality	Do you think that new fashion of cloth is not harmful for your society	Would you like to purchase new fashion clothes rather than old fashion clothes	Do you think that new fashion of clothes is accepted by your society
Valid	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	1.75	2.47	2.78	3.04	2.84	2.43	2.06	2.45	3.51	2.29	3.49	2.04	3.71	3.35	3.29
Range	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	4

Multi nominal Regression

Case Processing Summary

		N	Marginal Percentage
Do you feel choice difficulty while purchasing the new fashion clothes	strongly agree	46	45.1%
	agree	38	37.3%
	neither agree nor disagree	16	15.7%
	disagree	2	2.0%
Actors/focus group can affect on your fashion of clothes	strongly agree	14	13.7%
	agree	34	33.3%
	neither agree nor disagree	46	45.1%
	disagree	8	7.8%
New fashion of clothes is affordable for you	strongly agree	2	2.0%
	agree	40	39.2%
	neither agree or disagree	38	37.3%
	disagree	22	21.6%
Can new fashion of clothes fulfills your demand	agree	32	31.4%
	neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3%
	disagree	32	31.4%
	strongly disagree	2	2.0%
You purchase on your choice or depend on others	agree	30	29.4%
	neither agree nor disagree	58	56.9%
	disagree	14	13.7%
Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your culture	strongly agree	16	15.7%
	agree	42	41.2%
	neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5%
	disagree	16	15.7%
Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your religion	strongly agree	16	15.7%
	agree	68	66.7%
	neither agree nor disagree	14	13.7%
	disagree	4	3.9%
Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is costly for you	strongly agree	10	9.8%
	agree	50	49.0%
	neither agree nor disagree	30	29.4%
	disagree	10	9.8%
	strongly disagree	2	2.0%
Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is adopted by you	strongly agree	2	2.0%
	agree	6	5.9%
	neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3%
	disagree	54	52.9%
	strongly disagree	4	3.9%
Do you feel that new	strongly agree	10	9.8%

fashion can make your personality better	agree	58	56.9%
	neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5%
	disagree	6	5.9%
In your opinion new fashion trends are better than old fashion trends	strongly agree	6	5.9%
	agree	12	11.8%
	neither agree nor disagree	24	23.5%
	disagree	46	45.1%
Do you think new fashion trends are enhancing your personality	strongly disagree	14	13.7%
	strongly agree	22	21.6%
	agree	58	56.9%
	neither agree nor disagree	18	17.6%
Do you think that new fashion of cloth is not harmful for your society	disagree	4	3.9%
	strongly agree	2	2.0%
	agree	4	3.9%
	neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5%
	disagree	56	54.9%
Would you like to purchase new fashion clothes rather than old fashion clothes	strongly disagree	12	11.8%
	strongly agree	2	2.0%
	agree	18	17.6%
	neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5%
	disagree	50	49.0%
Do you think that new fashion of clothes is accepted by your society	strongly disagree	4	3.9%
	strongly agree	6	5.9%
	agree	10	9.8%
	neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3%
	disagree	48	47.1%
Valid	strongly disagree	2	2.0%
		102	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		102	

Frequency Table**Do you feel choice difficulty while purchasing the new fashion clothes**

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	46	45.1	45.1	45.1
agree	38	37.3	37.3	82.4
neither agree nor disagree	16	15.7	15.7	98.0
disagree	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Actors/focus group can affect on your fashion of clothes

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	14	13.7	13.7	13.7
agree	34	33.3	33.3	47.1
neither agree nor disagree	46	45.1	45.1	92.2
disagree	8	7.8	7.8	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Can new fashion of clothes fulfills your demand

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid agree	32	31.4	31.4	31.4
neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3	35.3	66.7
disagree	32	31.4	31.4	98.0
strongly disagree	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

You purchase on your choice or depend on others

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid agree	30	29.4	29.4	29.4
neither agree nor disagree	58	56.9	56.9	86.3
disagree	14	13.7	13.7	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your culture

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	16	15.7	15.7	15.7
agree	42	41.2	41.2	56.9
neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5	27.5	84.3
disagree	16	15.7	15.7	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your religion

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	16	15.7	15.7	15.7
agree	68	66.7	66.7	82.4
neither agree nor disagree	14	13.7	13.7	96.1
disagree	4	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is costly for you

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	10	9.8	9.8	9.8
agree	50	49.0	49.0	58.8
neither agree nor disagree	30	29.4	29.4	88.2
disagree	10	9.8	9.8	98.0
strongly disagree	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is adopted by you

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
agree	6	5.9	5.9	7.8
neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3	35.3	43.1
disagree	54	52.9	52.9	96.1
strongly disagree	4	3.9	3.9	100.0

Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is adopted by you

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
agree	6	5.9	5.9	7.8
neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3	35.3	43.1
disagree	54	52.9	52.9	96.1
strongly disagree	4	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Do you feel that new fashion can make your personality better

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	10	9.8	9.8	9.8
agree	58	56.9	56.9	66.7
neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5	27.5	94.1
disagree	6	5.9	5.9	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

In your opinion new fashion trends are better than old fashion trends

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	6	5.9	5.9	5.9
agree	12	11.8	11.8	17.6
neither agree nor disagree	24	23.5	23.5	41.2
disagree	46	45.1	45.1	86.3
strongly disagree	14	13.7	13.7	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Do you think new fashion trends are enhancing your personality

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	22	21.6	21.6	21.6
agree	58	56.9	56.9	78.4
neither agree nor disagree	18	17.6	17.6	96.1
disagree	4	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Do you think that new fashion of cloth is not harmful for your society

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
agree	4	3.9	3.9	5.9
neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5	27.5	33.3
disagree	56	54.9	54.9	88.2
strongly disagree	12	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Would you like to purchase new fashion clothes rather than old fashion clothes

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	2	2.0	2.0	2.0
agree	18	17.6	17.6	19.6
neither agree nor disagree	28	27.5	27.5	47.1
disagree	50	49.0	49.0	96.1
strongly disagree	4	3.9	3.9	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

Do you think that new fashion of clothes is accepted by your society

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid strongly agree	6	5.9	5.9	5.9
agree	10	9.8	9.8	15.7
neither agree nor disagree	36	35.3	35.3	51.0
disagree	48	47.1	47.1	98.0
strongly disagree	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	102	100.0	100.0	

QUESTIONNAIRE

Description	Strongly Agree 1	Agree 2	Neither Agree Nor Disagree 3	Disagree 4	Strongly Disagree 5
1-Do you feel choice difficulty while purchasing the new fashion clothes?					
2-Actors/focus group can affect on your fashion of clothes.					
3-New fashion of clothes is affordable for you.					
4-Can new fashion of clothes fulfills your demand?					
5-You purchase on your choice or depend on others.					
6-Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your culture.					
7-Can modern fashion of clothes affect on your religion.					
8-Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is costly for you?					
9-Do you feel that modern fashion of clothes is adopted by you?					
10-Do you feel that new fashion can make your personality better?					
11-In your opinion new fashion trends are better than old fashion trends.					
12-Do you think new fashion trends are enhancing your personality?					
13-Do you think that new fashion of cloth is not harmful for your society?					
14-Would you like to purchase new fashion clothes rather than old fashion clothes.					
15-Do you think that new fashion of clothes is accepted by your society?					